

MOSAIC ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY: A PANACEA FOR ENVIRONMENT SUSTAINABILITY AND DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

Dr. Okoroafor V.C. & Dr. (Mrs) Chukwuezi E.

Department of Religion and Cultural Studies, Alvan Ikoku University of Education, Owerri, Imo State

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Abstract: *Environment sustainability for life survival and development is a global concern. The consequences of environmental degradation are all embracing. Among other detrimental reactions is the significant increase in global warming. Conservation is needed in every aspect of our environment, be it the hydrosphere, lithosphere and atmosphere. Recently, it was reported that Nigeria is the most hit of the effects of deforestation. According to the United Nations (2022), Nigeria has the highest deforestation rate in the world with estimated 3.7% of forest lost every year. Religion as a social science, Christianity in particular seems to have a viable solution on environmental sustainability and development. This study exegezises on certain portions of the Pentateuch like Deuteronomy chapter 20:19-20; 22:6-7 and 23:9-15. Exegetical tools like Hebrew and Greek Lexicons, Concordance, Bible Commentaries and Bible Dictionaries were used to illicit information in this descriptive research design. The study discovered that, the Bible advocates for Eco-forestry, supports keystone species in conservation strategy and encourages environmental hygiene. Therefore, the paper recommends that Mosaic Environmental Policy be adopted in Nigeria for environmental sustainability and development. The writ concludes that if Mosaic Environmental Policy is not adopted in Nigeria, in the next decade there would be much loss of life as a result of environmental hazardousness.*

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INTRODUCTION

Sustainable development is synonymous to healthy environment. There could be no sustainable development in a deplorable environment. Unfortunately, it has been reported that Nigeria is the worst hit in environmental degradation. In biodiversity, some animals like the African Elephant, the Mountain Gorilla, the White Rhinoceros etc are under threat of extinction and are therefore endangered species (Sarojini, 2018). According to the United Nations (2022), Nigeria rank highest in deforestation rate in the world with estimated 3.7% of forest lost every year. Land erosion has also been threatening Nigerian environment.

As a result of these negative developments, the strategic objective of the National policy on environment is to coordinate environmental protection and natural resources conservation for sustainable development. To reach this goal, religion as one of the social sciences, especially, Christianity seems to have environmental policies and practices that could help Nigeria archive this lofty goal. This paper set forth to study the Mosaic policies and practices on environmental sustainability, especially on the areas of biodiversity conservation (Deut.22: 6-7), eco-forestry (Deut. 20:19-20) and close

system of refuse disposal (Deut.23:12).The study suggested ways Mosaic environmental policy could be applied in Nigeria for environmental sustainability and development in Nigeria.

II. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

A. Environmental Sustainability

According to Sphera (2020), environmental sustainability is the responsibility to conserve natural resources and protect global ecosystems to support health and wellbeing, now and in the future. The US Environmental Protection Agency puts it this way- it is “meeting today’s needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs”. Human wellbeing is closely linked to the health of the environment. Around the world, 24% of deaths can be traced back to avoidable environmental factors. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), in Sphera (2020), people need clean air to breath, fresh water to drink and places to live that are free from toxic substances and hazards. James (2023) gives more technical definition of sustainability. According to him, sustainability is understood as a form of intergenerational ethics in which the environmental and economic actions taken by present persons do not diminish the

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opportunities of future persons to enjoy similar levels of wealth utility, or welfare.

From the above definitions, we can safely deduct that environmental sustainability involves present persons taking responsibilities to conserve natural resources and preserve ecosystems for life and wellbeing now and for unabated enjoyment of the same or similar levels of wealth, utility or welfare by posterity.

B. Mosaic Environmental Policy

Mosaic Environmental Policy has to do with all the environmental regulations made by Moses in the Pentateuch (the Five Books of Moses) to ensure the conservation of natural resources and protect global ecosystems of present wellbeing and for future generation of Israel.

III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

There are several theories propounded about sustainability (1). The Economic Analysts Theory: According to James (2023) the Economic Analysts have some sometimes understood the concept in terms of non-declining per capital income flows over time, or long-term economic growth, with minimal environmental impacts and argued on how to maintain the capital endowments needed to sustain those income flows. James (2023) noticed that controversy over the substitutability of natural and human-made capital has divided proponents of weak and strong sustainability: the former argue that the two types of capital are largely interchangeable, on the other hand, the later

maintain that natural capital is increasingly the scarcest factor of production. It has been stressed that Ecosystem services, such as the provision of clean water or crop pollution, are often undervalued aspects of natural capital that should be incorporated into economic discussions of sustainability.

(2). Ecologists and Systems Theorists:

Ecologists and Systems Theorists have defined sustainability in terms of physical interdependencies, energy flows and population dynamics. They have emphasized the design features that suit social systems for long-term survival, including robustness, resiliency, redundancy and adaptability.

(3). Political Analysts Theorist:

Political Analysts Theorist focused on the ideological and normative implications of sustainability on the characters of green political projects, and on the public policy implications. This study adopts Ecologist and systems theorists' ideas, in particular, Fritjof Capra theory of "The Web of Life" whereby he explores the interconnectedness of living organisms and ecosystems and how understanding these complex relationships is crucial for sustainability. He also emphasizes the importance of applying system thinking to solve environmental challenges and promote a more sustainable future.

This theory fitted in very well in Mosaic environmental policy in that Mosaic

environmental policy understands the interconnectedness of living organisms and ecosystems and apply systems thinking to solve environmental challenges and encourages a more sustainable future.

There are many environmental hazards in Nigeria. For Example, erosion menace, air, water and land pollutions, deforestation dangers, improper waste disposal effects, etc. In order to combat environmental issues Nigerian government has set up some Agencies to tackle these challenges in the table below, showing some Nigeria Policies and Agencies and their Functions on Environmental Sustainability

IV. NIGERIAN ENVIRONMENTAL SITUATION: AN OVERVIEW

Table 1: Nigerian Policies/Agencies and Function on Environmental Sustainability

S/N	Policy/Agency/Body	Functions
1.	National Environmental Policy	The National Environmental policy borders on pollution control, biodiversity conservation, waste management and climate change.
2.	Paris Agreement and Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs)	This agreement is to enforce the reduction of greenhouse gas emission and enhance climate resilience.
3.	Ogoni clean-up project	This project was set to remediate and restore the environment in the Niger Delta region, which has been affected by oil pollution.
4.	Renewables and Energy Efficiency	This is to ensure that Nigeria’s aim of diversification of its energy sources by promoting renewable energy, like solar, wind, and hydro power, to reduce reliance on fossil fuels. Also, energy efficiency measures are emphasized too, to reduce energy consumption.
5.	Afforestation and Reforestation	This is government programs to combat deforestation and encourage afforestation and reforestation to enhance forest cover and preserve biodiversity.

6.	Waste Management	The functions of waste management include discovering ways of improving waste management systems, which involves recycling waste to energy projects. The aim of this is to reduce pollution and promote a circular economy.
7.	Sustainable Agriculture	The aim of this is to ensure sustainable agricultural practices and initiatives to boost food security, reduce land degradation and promote climate resilience.
8.	Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)	The EIA process is mandatory for development projects, ensuring that potential environmental impacts are considered and mitigated.

Despite all these policies and actions taken by Nigerian government to solve the problem of environmental disaster, yet Nigeria is threatened with serious environmental issues. Erosion has been threatening some Southeastern states such as Anambra, Enugu, Ebonyi, Imo and Abia. The devastating effects of erosion in these areas might be as a result of improper land management and absence of erosion control measures. Deforestation is another major environmental issue that has endangered environmental sustainability in Nigeria. Southern part of the Country like Cross River, Edo, Ondo, Delta and Bayelsa are the most affected. Because of this unresolved environmental issue, this paper looks into Mosaic environmental practices for a solution.

V. MOSAIC ENVIRONMENTAL GUIDELINES

A. In Biodiversity Conservation

Biodiversity which is the richness in variety and variability of species of all living organisms (Sharma, 2015) is provided for in Mosaic environmental laws.

(1). Keystone Species Conservation Strategy (In-Situ Approach) is prescribed by Mosaic Environmental Guidelines

Keystone species are category of organisms within biological communities whose presence determine the ability of large number of other species to persist in the community (Paine, 1966 in Sandhya, 2022). For example, the lion as a keystone species, according to Pippa (2021) plays role as large predator (among other things) is responsible for keeping prey populations under control and removing sick,

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week or genetically compromised animals from the system. The hen is also a keystone species.

In the Mosaic guidelines of environmental regulations, “in-situ” approach is approved. In biodiversity conservation strategies “in-situ”

(i). Exegesis and Interpretation of Deuteronomy 22: 6-7

The text reads: “if a bird’s nest happens to be before you along the way, in any tree or on the ground, with young ones or eggs, with the mother sitting on the young or on the eggs. You shall not take the mother with the young. You shall surely let the mother go, and take the young for yourself, that it may be well with you and that you may prolong your days”.

The Hebrew word **צִפּוֹר** . “sippor” is used instead of **אִמ** “em”. **אִמ** is a primitive word meaning “mother” as in the bond of the family. The adult strong mother protecting the weak offspring. But **צִפּוֹר** . “sippor” which has the overall sense of a weakling, is used. “Sippor” is a singular common noun denoting “a little bird” (as hopping). Birds in this category are fowl and sparrow. (Strong, 2007). **צִפּוֹר** . Sippor” has

Hence the instruction-you shall not take away the principal figure or factor (the mother) among them, so as to preserve their posterity.

Tokunboh (2006) from his own perspective, commenting on this passage writes;

The reason for this instruction is probably not some sentimental associations with motherhood

conservation has to do with the conservation of genetic resources through their maintenance within natural or even in human-made eco systems in which they occur.

the same root with **צָפַר**. “sapar” meaning to skip about, (that is return, depart early).

Here, all (both the entire mother, young ones and eggs) are depicted as weak and hopping, skipping about to return to source and not to drift away. Another Hebrew word with the same root **צָפַת** “Sapa” means to properly lean forward, to look out for, expect help. The picture painted here is as if to say the little creatures are begging for help and protection of their lives and posterity. Derek (1997) maintains that the house sparrow is very common in Palestine and almost identical to the West European bird. Derek (1997) argues that it could be referred to in Mt. 10: 29, although, the original word implies other assorted small birds which were (and are) killed and sold. Derek (1997)’s description of the sparrow as common is correct. In Mt. 10:29 Jesus stresses that although the sparrow is common yet God cares for them.

but the fact that by preserving the mother bird she would be in a position to lay another clutch of eggs and raise younger ones, thus protecting the species and supplying more food. What we have here is an example of early conservation legislation.

Howley et al (1979) describes this text as “another humanitarian law, with ecological values.

Both Howley et al (1979) and Tokunboh (2006) are correct in their commentaries on this passage. The Bible establishes its support and concern for keystone species in conservation strategy.

(2). Eco-Forestry is Another Environmental Conservation Strategy approved by Mosaic Regulation

Eco-forestry is a forest management practice that maintains or restores natural ecosystem richness, complexity and resilience, while providing for ecologically appropriate levels of harvest (Merve, 2020). The bottom line of eco-forestry is not only to naturally resuscitate the forest and insurance of forest consistency year in, year out but also to maintain ecological integrity. Ecological integrity is the insurance that the forest is at the state of being whole, entire, undiminished and functional.

According to Merve (2020), in eco-forestry, losing species or dangerously diminishing their natural abundance is not acceptable. They have intrinsic value and valuable functions in the ecosystem. In other words, timber is not of greater importance than biodiversity, hydrology, climate moderation, soil health, edible plants, recreation etc. The philosophy behind this rationale is that the natural world is the basis for our existence and the basis for our economy.

Merve (2020) cited Eco-forestry Institute Society’s (EIS) commanded practices of Eco-forest management. The principles are stated below

1. It carefully chooses trees to fall according to its list of ranked selection criteria which focus on ecological integrity and safety.
 2. It uses low impact harvesting techniques and leaves branches and tops as well as other low-market-values pieces where tree fell.
 3. Tree species which are less frequent at wildwood are receiving greater attention for retention.
 4. The market value of tree species will not influence tree species composition at wildwood.
 5. No synthetic chemicals (i.e fertilizer, herbicides, insecticides, fungicides) will be applied.
 6. EIS rely on natural regeneration (seeding) from the most successfully, old trees. Therefore, in the practice of eco-forestry, certain trees are selectively harvested while causing minimal damage to the rest of the forest. The rationale behind this method is to systematically fell mature trees while leaving the forest ecosystem relatively unaffected. The keywords in EIS eco-forestry practice is naturalism, selectivity (carefully choosing), intact, preservation of biodiversity, benevolent treatment of forest. In fact, in eco-forestry trees gain human “respect”
- i). Exegesis and Interpretation of Deuteronomy 20: 19-20

Now, let's consider the Christian view on Eco-forestry.

The Text reads:

“19... you shall not destroy its trees by wielding and ax against them; if you can eat of them, do not cut them down to use in the siege, for the tree of the field is man's food (Man's life: King James Version KJV).

1). Friendliness with the trees or forest because of their indispensability in human life:

The Hebrew sentence **לֹא תִשָּׂחַת** (you read from right to left in Hebrew language) “*litph shahat*” means “you shall not destroy”.

The Hebrew word “**שָׂחַת**” *shahat* translated “destroy” has a primitive root denoting to decay, (that is causatively) ruin (literally or figuratively): batter, cast off, corrupt, lose, mar perish, spill waste etc. So Israel was forbidden (v)Discouraging practices that can cause the trees or forest to ruin, decay, corrupt, mar or waste. The reason for this, perhaps might be because

the trees of the forest is man's “**נֶפֶשׁ**” *nephesh* “life”. KJV translation is preferred to NKJV that translated it “man's food” because the Hebrew word used here is not “**לֶחֶם**” *lehem* “food” but “**נֶפֶשׁ**”

New Revised Standard Version (NRSV) went so far to render the verse this way: “Are trees in the field human beings that they should come under siege from you?” The sense that runs all

20. Only the trees which you know are not trees for food you may destroy and cut down....”

The key concepts in this passage includes (i). Friendliness with the trees of forest because of their indispensability in human life, (ii). Selectivity: careful choosing of the ones that may be cut down (iii) Natural regeneration: that is, new trees sprouting from healthy old ones. (iv). Insurance of unceasing existence of forest.

through this scenario is friendliness of trees to man, they are not enemies but needful for man's continual existence. Therefore, they should not be destroyed.

ii. Selectivity: Only the trees that are not for food, may be cut down:

The Hebrew wordings “**רַק עֵץ אֲשֶׁר-סוּעַ בִּי לֹא-עֵץ מֵן**” *raq es' esher to'bi li' es me'*. Rendered “only the trees which you know are not trees for food you may destroy and cut down,” denotes selectivity. The Hebrew word ‘**רַק**’ *raq* “only” as a noun, has sense of “leanness” that is (figuratively) limitation. This means that Israel has a lean chance in cutting any tree even if is not for food. The allowance of tree cutting is limited. They are not to cut trees indiscriminately. It becomes imperative that the trees to cut would be carefully chosen. Even the need of wood for siege does not warrant tree cutting “...do not cut them down to use in the siege “(Deut. 20:20). Through this way, the forest is maintained undiminished.

iii. Natural: No Artificial Application to the Forest.

The Bible did not make mention of artificial reforestation, neither has condemned it either. Being silent over the issue would mean leaving the stumps and roots of cut trees to sprout new ones. This is natural regeneration. New trees grow out of the stumps and roots of old healthy trees seeding from the most successful, old trees. Application of human instruments against the trees is hardly allowed- “...you shall not destroy its trees by wielding an ax against them...” In the practice of eco-forestry applications of fertilizer, herbicides, insecticides, fungicides etc in the wildwood is forbidden.

iv). Ceaseless Existence of Forest (insurance of Forest in a particular Area, year in year out)

Israel is to be selective in tree cutting. This policy negates the practice of “clear cutting” which involves the cutting of all trees in an area at one time. With eco-forestry techniques, there is permanent existence of forest year in year out.

v). Ecological Integrity is Maintained

From the foregoing, we have seen that the Christian perspective of eco-forestry contains almost all the features, traits and characteristics of eco-forestry. It ensures that forest is whole, entire, undiminished and functional.

3). In Waste Disposal Management Close System (Compost Pit) is supported by Mosaic Environmental Guidelines

Waste can be seen as anything that no longer has an apparent value to the owner, nevertheless, it might be not yet completely valueless, to someone else (Hassan et al, 2019). Waste Disposal Management is the way in which those things that are no longer valuable to an individual is removed in environmental sanitation. Close system of waste disposal management has to do with non-open techniques of waster removal.

i). Critical Study of Deuteronomy 23: 12-13

The text reads

“also, you shall have a place outside the camp where you may go out; you shall dig with it, and turn and cover your refuse”.

This passage reveals that Mosaic environmental guidelines recommended close system waste disposal management. The Israelites were instructed to dig a pit, after defecation, they should turn around and cover the feces.

According to Hassan et al (2019), the largest volume of liquid waste comes from the human feces... open system of waste disposal has many dangers. Inhaling of the odor emitting from the open waste can cause disease. Common among these diseases are malaria fever, cholera and typhoid. When waste is disposed without being covered, when burnt, leads to air pollution. This

may have negative effect on the quality of air we breathe and on asthmatic persons. Again, if this waste is thrown or poured (discharged) into streams and rivers, it can block the flow of water. The water becomes a ground for breeding unwanted insects. This will also make the water unsafe for use by people living downstream.

VI. REALIZING ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY AND DEVELOPMENT VIA APPLICATION OF MOSAIC ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY.

A. Application of Keystone species conservation strategy – “in-situ” Approach for Development in Nigeria

When Nigeria adopts and apply keystone species conservation strategy -in-situ” approach, it will enhance Nigerian development in the following ways:

i). Persisting Undiminished Biodiversity

When Nigeria achieves persistent undiminished Biodiversity, its grantees friendly atmosphere that is conducive for life. This good condition would result good health and favourable ground for agriculture.

ii). “In-situ” Approach saves money for other Development

Nigeria will save much money that would have been spent on artificial habitat on other development.

iii). Many species are saved

Many species are saved that would have been lost in any unfavourable condition of artificial habitat.

B. Application of Eco-Forestry for Development in Nigeria

i). Natural Resuscitation of the Forest Saves Expenses

The money for new seedlings and labour would be directed to another investment as the natural trees are allowed to resuscitate by themselves.

ii). Ecological Integrity Yields benefits to the Society

When the forest is at the state of being whole, entire, undiminished and functional year in year out, some intrinsic benefits like natural freshness and lack of global warming occur. So, timber is not of greater importance than biodiversity, hydrology, climate moderation, soil health, edible plants and recreation which ecological integrity produce.

C). Application of close system waste disposal management for development in Nigeria

i). Close system waste disposal management is the most disease-controlled type of waste disposal

The toxic that would have emitted from the waste is prevented by the covering of the waste. Prevention of disease is better than cure. Huge amount of money is spent for health when somebody is sick and many at times, after spending money good health is not achieved.

The money gained from prevention of sickness is used for further development.

iii). Close system waste disposal management is the most assuring environmental sanitation provider

When waste is not covered, it constitutes an eye saw. Littered environment is unhealthy.

VII. SUMMARY

Mosaic environmental policy approved keystone species in conservation strategy, eco-forestry and closed system of waste disposal management and they make for environmental sustainability and development.

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VIII. CONCLUSION

As Nigeria is not left out in environmental degradation, if effort is not beefed up in adopting Mosaic Environmental Policy, there will increase in climate change in Nigeria.

IX. Recommendations

This writ recommends that Mosaic environmental guidelines namely; keystone species in conservation strategy, eco-forestry and closed system of waste disposal management be adopted in Nigerian environmental issues.

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